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Key Points:

- Differences between digital elevation models (DEMs) (i.e., their absolute vertical accuracy) have a lower effect on stream delineation than terrain slope and landcover
- The use of higher-resolution DEMs to derive stream networks increases the importance of removing vegetation and building bias
- Vertical accuracy alone does not reflect DEMs' performance in stream delineation, emphasizing the need to include this in quality evaluation

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Choosing the Optimal Global Digital Elevation Model for Stream Network Delineation: Beyond Vertical Accuracy

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Abstract Satellite-derived global digital elevation models (DEMs) are essential for providing the topographic information needed in a wide range of hydrological applications. However, their use is limited by spatial resolution and vertical bias due to sensor limitations in observing bare terrain. Significant efforts have been made to improve the resolution of global DEMs (e.g., TanDEM-X) and create bare-earth DEMs (e.g., FABDEM, MERIT, CEDTM). We evaluated the vertical accuracy of bare-earth and global DEMs in Central European mountains and submontane regions, and assessed how DEM resolution, vegetation offset removal, land cover, and terrain slope affect stream network delineation. Using lidar-derived DTM and national stream networks as references, we found that: (a) bare-earth DEMs outperform global DEMs across all land cover types. RMSEs increased with increasing slope for all DEMs in non-forest areas. In forests, however, the negative effect of the slope was outweighed by the vegetation offset even for bare-earth DTMs; (b) the accuracy of derived stream networks was affected by terrain slope and land cover more than by the vertical accuracy of DEMs. Stream network delineation performed poorly in non-forest areas and relatively well in forests. Increasing slope improved the streams delineation performance; (c) using DEMs with higher resolution (e.g., 12 m TanDEM-X) improved stream network delineation, but increasing resolution also increased the need for effective vegetation bias removal. Our results indicate that vertical accuracy alone does not reflect how well DEMs perform in stream network delineation. This underscores the need to include stream network performance in DEM quality rankings.

Plain Language Summary We evaluated the accuracy of different types of digital elevation models (DEMs) and derived stream networks in Central European mountains. Our focus was on satellite-derived global DEMs, including bare-earth DEMs (i.e., DEMs with vegetation and building offsets removed). Using lidar DTM and national stream networks as references, we found that bare-earth DEMs consistently outperformed other DEMs across all evaluated land cover types. We observed that slope and land cover have contrasting effects on the accuracy of DEMs and delineated stream networks. As slope increases, DEMs accuracy decreases, while for delineated stream networks, the opposite trend is observed. Where land cover is concerned, DEMs' vertical accuracies (i.e., how well they represent the bare-earth terrain) are lowest in forests, whereas the accuracy of stream network is lowest in non-forest areas. Furthermore, we demonstrated that slope and land cover type considerably affect the accuracy of stream network delineation, more so than the vertical accuracy of the DEMs. Additionally, we found that using DEMs with higher resolution can improve stream network delineation, but increasing resolution also increases the need for effective vegetation bias removal. Therefore, removing vegetation and buildings offset from Tandem-X DEM at a 12 m resolution would represent a major next step forward.

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1. Introduction

Global space-borne digital elevation models (DEMs) have become an essential and often the only source of topographic information. Over the past two decades, major efforts have been made to develop high-quality global DEMs, with several space-borne missions carried out with this goal (Abrams et al., 2010; Farr et al., 2007; Krieger

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et al., 2013; Tadono et al., 2014). These efforts resulted in global or near-global DEMs with resolutions finer than 100 m, such as the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM; Rabus et al., 2003), TerraSAR-X add-on for Digital Elevation Measurement (TanDEM-X; Rizzoli et al., 2017), Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer Global Digital Elevation Model (ASTER GDEM; Abrams et al., 2010), or Advanced Land Observing Satellite World 3D (ALOS World 3D; Tadono et al., 2014).

Global DEMs constitute an important data source for flood susceptibility mapping (e.g., Shah et al., 2022; Shrestha et al., 2021; Tariku et al., 2021; Wasko et al., 2021; Whitfield, 2012; Zhang et al., 2022) and are used for deriving seamless river networks suited to global scale applications, such as the HydroSHEDS database (Lehner & Grill, 2013), the Global River Topology (GRIT) data set (Wortmann et al., 2024), and the MERIT Hydro data set (Yamazaki et al., 2019). However, global DEMs do not represent the bare ground elevation (i.e., digital terrain model; DTM). They contain considerable vertical bias due to sensors' limitations to observe terrain below vegetation canopies and buildings, which results in overestimation of the terrain height (Bielski et al., 2023; Gdulová et al., 2020). This is particularly problematic for applications in hydrology, such as delineating river networks (Boulton & Stokes, 2018; Metz et al., 2011; Mukherjee et al., 2013; Nguyen et al., 2023; Pandya et al., 2024; Veregin, 1997) and flood modeling (Archer et al., 2018; Cea et al., 2024; Courty et al., 2019; Hawker et al., 2018; Sampson et al., 2015; Teng et al., 2022).

DTMs obtained through laser altimetry, commonly referred to as Light Detection and Ranging (lidar), are considered the optimal source of topographic data. Airborne laser scanning (ALS), where a lidar sensor is mounted on an aircraft, has emerged as the main method for capturing terrain information over large areas (Wehr & Lohr, 1999). The ability to capture the terrain under the vegetation canopy is considered the key advantage of lidar (Klápště et al., 2020; Štroner et al., 2022). Lidar-based DTMs are increasingly available in high-income countries—many European countries have made their national ALS data public (Moudrý et al., 2023); still, in low-income countries, such models remain often unavailable. Moreover, ALS-derived DTMs are still fragmented and exist only for individual countries (e.g., Assmann et al., 2022), with no seamless product for large territorial units (e.g., Europe) in sight (but see 3D Elevation Program; Stoker & Miller, 2022). So far, combining ALS data from multiple countries for large-scale studies is virtually impossible as it would be too time-consuming. Therefore, many researchers continue to rely on the global DEMs as a surrogate for ALS-derived digital terrain models (e.g., Cea et al., 2024; Farooq et al., 2019; Garrote, 2022).

The range of available global DEMs is continuously increasing and users are facing the dilemma of choosing the appropriate DEM (Bielski et al., 2023). Available DEMs differ in their processing level, which may not be adequate for hydrological applications. TanDEM-X, at a 12 m spatial resolution, is the finest resolution global product currently available. However, it is an unedited DEM derived from interferometric radar processing and mosaicking only and, as such, may contain voids (Rizzoli et al., 2017). Copernicus DEM is mainly based on TanDEM-X data, but additional global DEMs, such as SRTM and ASTER, were used to some extent to fill voids and reduce the error in problematic areas (Franks & Rengarajan, 2023; Marešová et al., 2021). However, all above-mentioned DEMs suffer from systematic overestimation of terrain due to the aboveground objects (such as vegetation and buildings), the height of which is included in the models (Carabajal & Harding, 2006; Gamba et al., 2002; Gdulová et al., 2020; Hawker et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2021). Consequently, this generates notable variations in accuracy among various land cover types (e.g., Gdulová et al., 2020; Nelson et al., 2009), limiting the use of global DEMs in hydrological modeling.

To improve the applicability of global DEMs in hydrological modeling, additional processing is required to enhance accuracy (e.g., Hawker et al., 2022; Sampson et al., 2015). This includes, in particular, the removal of vegetation-caused bias (Gallant & Read, 2016; O'Loughlin et al., 2016; Kulp & Strauss, 2018; Narin et al., 2024). Several global DEMs with vegetation offset removed (or minimized) have been produced. Yamazaki et al. (2017) developed the Multi-Error-Removed Improved-Terrain (MERIT) model, a high-accuracy global DTM at a 90 m resolution produced by eliminating multiple error components, including the vegetation offset (but not buildings). Another such effort was presented by the Continental Europe Digital Terrain Model (CEDTM) by Hengl et al. (2020). More recently, Hawker et al. (2022) developed the Forest And Buildings-Removed Copernicus DEM (FABDEM), the first global DEM with forests and buildings removed at a 30 m resolution. In addition, the German Aerospace Agency (DLR) is working on a hydrologically pre-conditioned version of the TanDEM-X DEM at a 30 m resolution that will be used to produce a new version of HydroSHEDS (v2) at the same resolution, planned for release in 2024 (<https://www.hydrosheds.org/hydrosheds-v2>). Nonetheless, techniques

Figure 1. Workflow of the study. We assessed the vertical accuracy (Section 3.1) of eight DEMs (Input data) and their applicability for stream network delineation (Section 3.2). In both tests, we evaluated the effect of land cover (forest, non-forest, and built-up areas) and terrain slope on the accuracy. For validation, we used a lidar-derived DTM and national stream networks (Reference data).

employed to eliminate vegetation offsets rely on maps of tree cover and vegetation height from multiple independent sources with their own accuracy issues (Bolton et al., 2013; Moudry et al., 2024; Pascual et al., 2022). Moreover, the accuracy of vegetation-free DEMs can exhibit substantial differences across regions (Li et al., 2023; Saberi et al., 2023).

Studies typically evaluate the quality of DEMs by assessing their absolute vertical accuracy (see the review by López-Vázquez & Ariza-López, 2023); however, this measure may not fully capture their suitability for hydrological applications (Bielski et al., 2023; Trevisani et al., 2023). While several studies have explored the suitability of individual DEMs for stream network delineation and flood modeling (e.g., Hawker et al., 2019; McMaster, 2002; Meadows et al., 2024; Nguyen et al., 2023; Sampson et al., 2016; Uemaa et al., 2020; Xafoulis et al., 2023), there is still uncertainty of whether DEM resolution or vegetation offset removal is more crucial for accurate stream network delineation. Additionally, the interaction of these characteristics with land cover and terrain slope — factors known to significantly impact DEM accuracy and stream network delineation (e.g., Li et al., 2022; Moges et al., 2023; Rahman et al., 2010; Veregin, 1997; Yan et al., 2020) — remains unclear. Therefore, this study aims to examine the vertical accuracy of eight global DEMs and their usability for stream network delineation in a mountainous region of Central Europe. In particular, we assess (a) the error in global DEMs and the success of vegetation and buildings removal in bare-earth DEMs; (b) the effect of land cover (forests, non-forest, and build-up areas) and terrain slope on the DEMs and delineated stream networks accuracy, and (c) whether the higher resolution DEM (e.g., TanDEM-X at 12 m resolution) or DEM with vegetation offset removed (e.g., FABDEM at 30 m resolution) is more suitable for accurate stream network delineation (See Figure 1 for the overall workflow of the study).

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Study Area

The study area covers the Giant Mountains and their vicinity (Figure 2). The Giant mountains are located on the border between Czechia and Poland, with the main ridge of the mountains forming the state border, and cover

Figure 2. The reference stream network acquired from the Digital Database of Water Management Data (www.dibavod.cz; Czechia) and Polish National Geoportal (geoportal.gov.pl; Poland) in comparison to global river networks data sets. HydroRivers and GRIT are available in vector format. MERIT Hydro provides the upstream drainage area raster, and the stream network was delineated using the same settings as networks evaluated in this study (see Data and methods section). Note the relatively coarse resolution of global river network data sets, which often misrepresents the river network at a regional scale.

about 1,200 km² (15°25′–15°50′E and 50°38′–50°50′N). The altitudes range between 300 and 1,600 m a.m.s.l. The tree line traverses the altitudinal range of 1,200–1,350 m a.m.s.l. and vegetation consists of croplands and pastures, natural grasslands, spruce monocultures, and remnants of original deciduous and mixed mountain forests. The terrain characteristics of the Czech and Polish sides differ slightly. On the Czech (southern) side, the terrain slopes are more gradual, and the gentle transition from the highlands to the lowlands is characterized by extensive glacial features, including U-shaped valleys, cirques, and moraine deposits. In contrast, on the Polish (northern) side, the terrain shows more abrupt transitions from high elevations of the mountain range to the lower-lying areas, resulting in relatively steep slopes and deep valleys leading to a rapid drop in elevation and transition into a flat submontane terrain on the Polish side. This gives us the opportunity to compare the performance of the studied models in both types of terrain. The main ridge acts as a hydrological divide, separating drainage basins that flow in different directions. On the Czech side, rivers drain into the Elbe river basin and, consequently, to the North Sea, while on the Polish side of the ridge, watercourses generally flow into the Oder river basin and to the Baltic Sea. The different terrain characters result in different drainage patterns on either side. On the Czech side, rivers tend to have shorter, steeper courses. In contrast, on the Polish side, watercourses may exhibit longer, more meandering paths (Figure 2).

2.2. Reference ALS and Stream Network Data

The ALS data for the Czech and Polish parts of the Giant Mountains were acquired in 2012 during the leaf-on period using a small-footprint airborne lidar system (RIEGL LMS Q-680i). The point clouds for the Czech part were provided by the State Administration of Land Surveying and Cadaster. The horizontal datum is the Datum of Uniform Trigonometric Cadastral Network (S-JTSK; EPSG: 5514) and the vertical datum is the

Table 1
Overview of the Evaluated Global DEMs

Global DEM	Abbreviated	Horizontal datum	Vertical datum	Resolution [m]	Source
Shuttle radar topography mission	SRTM90	WGS84	EGM96	90	https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/
NASA digital elevation model	NASA30	WGS84	EGM96	30	https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/
TerraSAR-X add-on for digital elevation measurement	TDX12, TDX90	WGS84	WGS84	12, 90	https://geoservice.dlr.de/web/
Copernicus DEM GLO-30	COP30	WGS84	EGM2008	30	https://spacedata.copernicus.eu
Multi-error-removed improved-terrain DEM	MERIT90	WGS84	EGM96	90	http://hydro.iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp/~yamada/
Forest and buildings removed DEM	FAB30	WGS84	EGM2008	30	https://data.bris.ac.uk/data/
Continental Europe DEM	CON30	WGS84	EGM2008	30	https://ecodatacube.eu/

Baltic Vertical Datum—after adjustment (Bpv; EPSG: 5705). The ALS data for the Polish part were collected during the nationwide project—IT System for the Country's Protection project (ISOK project) managed by the Main Office of Geodesy and Cartography in Poland, and the data are available for download from the Polish National Geoportal. The horizontal datum is PL-KRON86-NH and the vertical datum is CS92. The point cloud density of both point clouds was at least 4 points per m² and both point clouds were already classified. We used the ground points to generate a digital terrain model (DTM) at a 2 m resolution (hereafter lidar DTM) and manually edited the resulting DTM to remove bridges as they can pose problems in generating the stream network.

The reference stream network data (Figure 2) for Czechia were acquired from the Digital Database of Water Management Data (DIBAVOD), developed by the T.G. Masaryk Water Research Institute (Fojtk et al., 2022). The reference stream network data for Poland were acquired from the Polish National Geoportal from the Topographic Objects Database (BDOT10k), managed by the Head Office of Geodesy and Cartography. These databases were originally created by vectorizing the digitized Base Map of the respective country at a scale of 1:10,000. The absolute position of stream networks was subsequently refined and updated using orthophotos, airborne laser scanning, and/or field surveys to ensure the accuracy and relevance of the data. This makes them suitable for use as a reference data in our analysis. These data are now part of a digital database used to create base maps of both countries.

2.3. Radar Derived Global DEMs

The global DEMs used in this study originate from two radar missions, namely the SRTM and the TanDEM-X mission. Three additional models represent the so-called “bare earth” DEMs that were created by modifying the original models, mainly by removing vertical bias caused by vegetation and buildings. Table 1 shows the basic characteristics of the missions and global DEMs used in this study.

2.3.1. Original DEMs (SRTM, NASADEM, TanDEM-X, Copernicus)

The Shuttle radar topography mission took 11 days in February 2000 and collected C-band synthetic aperture radar data over continental areas between 60° north latitude and 56° south latitude. Each location was captured at least twice (on the ascending and descending orbit) to minimize the occurrence of areas without data coverage due to the radar shadow effect (Farr et al., 2007). We downloaded the void-filled (C band) version SRTM DEM v3 with a 3-arcsecond resolution (hereafter referred to as SRTM90). NASADEM was released in February 2020 and represents a modernization of the SRTM. It results from complete re-processing of the raw SRTM C-band radar echo and telemetry data, void reductions by merging with refined ASTER GDEM and AW3D30 DEM elevations, and improved vertical adjustments using the Ice, Cloud, and Land Elevation Satellite (ICESat) laser profiles and improved quality assessments and adjustments (Buckley et al., 2020; Crippen et al., 2016). We used the NASADEM at a 1 arc-second resolution (hereafter referred to as NASA30).

TanDEM-X is an Earth observation radar mission that consists of a SAR interferometer built by two almost identical satellites (TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X) flying in close formation (Rizzoli et al., 2017). The mission's primary objective was to generate a global, consistent, and high-resolution DEM. The sensors took imagery of the

Earth's surface multiple times from different orbit positions between 2010 and 2015. The resulting DEM is thus based on multiple overflights, reducing the number of locations with erroneously captured data due to radar shadow or layover effects (Gdulová et al., 2020; Rizzoli et al., 2017). Here, we used TanDEM-X with a spatial resolution of 3-arcseconds (hereafter referred to as TDX90) and 0.4-arcsecond (provided by the German Aerospace Center; hereafter referred to as TDX12).

The Copernicus DEM was derived from the TanDEM-X WorldDEM™, which is based on TanDEM-X and was subject to terrain correction and hydrological editing. Terrain correction consisted of spikes and holes removal, identification and filling of voids (small voids were interpolated, and larger voids were infilled with an alternate DEM), and identification and correction of systematic and random biases (Collins et al., 2015; Guth & Geoffroy, 2021; Marešová et al., 2021). We used the Copernicus DEM (version GLO-30) at a 1-arcsecond resolution (hereafter referred to as COP30).

2.3.2. Vegetation (Buildings) Removed DEMs (MERIT, FABDEM, CEDTM)

Multi-Error-Removed Improved-Terrain (MERIT) DEM is a global DTM at a 3-arcseconds resolution with vegetation offset removed (Yamazaki et al., 2017). The MERIT DEM was created from the SRTM3 DEM v2.1 (below N60°; note that all our study areas are below that latitude) and AW3D30 DEM v1 version (above N60°) by eliminating major error components, including vegetation bias (but not buildings) and random errors (i.e., absolute bias, stripe noise, and speckle noise; hereafter referred to as MERIT90).

Forest And Buildings Removed Copernicus DEM (FABDEM) is the first global digital elevation model with forests and buildings removed at a 1-arcsecond resolution. Hawker et al. (2022) utilized machine learning techniques and auxiliary data on global buildings and forest coverage to remove vegetation and buildings' vertical offset from the Copernicus DEM. They reported improvement in absolute vertical error from 1.61 to 1.12 m and from 5.15 to 2.88 m in built-up areas and forests, respectively. FABDEM is available between 60° S and 80° N at a 1-arcsecond resolution (hereafter referred to as FAB30).

The Continental Europe Digital Terrain Model (CEDTM) is based on several publicly available DEMs and predicted using Ensemble Machine Learning (Hengl et al., 2020). Ensemble Machine Learning was trained using space-borne lidar measurements representing terrain height (GEDI, ICESat-2), publicly available DEMs (AW3D30, Copernicus DEM, EUDEM, and MERIT), and background layers (canopy height, tree cover, and surface water cover maps) to predict the most probable bare-earth terrain height (Hengl et al., 2020). We downloaded the Continental Europe Digital Terrain Model at a 1-arcsecond resolution (hereafter referred to as CON30).

2.4. Horizontal and Vertical Datum Conversion

In order to mutually compare all the models (Table 1), we transformed them into the ETRS89/UTM zone 33N coordinate system using the bilinear resampling method. TanDEM-X elevations correspond to ellipsoidal heights while other evaluated DEMs represent the orthometric heights. To match the heights of TanDEM-X with the remaining DEMs, a quasigeoid of Czechia and the surrounding areas was used. The quasigeoid is an ASCII file that contains 53,550 positions of latitude, longitude (grid of 1' × 1.5'), and the height of the quasigeoid across Czechia. We interpolated the quasigeoid to the same spatial resolution as TanDEM-X using universal kriging and subsequently subtracted it from the TanDEM-X.

2.5. Environmental Characteristics (Land Cover, Slope)

The accuracy in various land cover categories is often evaluated and reported to assist users in selecting optimal models (e.g., Hawker et al., 2019). Hence, to assess the vertical accuracy of DEMs and the delineated stream networks with respect to the vegetation cover and to evaluate the success of the vegetation and building offset removal in corrected DEMs, we calculated the accuracy measures separately for agricultural areas (hereafter non-forest areas), forest areas and urban areas. To reduce the potential impact of temporality, we used only areas for which no land cover changes were recorded between 2000 and 2012. We obtained land cover data for both years from the Corine land cover database with a resolution of 100 m.

Terrain slope is another environmental characteristic with a considerable effect on DEMs and the delineated stream network accuracy (Carrera-Hernandez, 2021; Gdulová et al., 2020; Jing et al., 2014; Yap et al., 2019).

Therefore, we assessed the effect of terrain slope on DEMs and streams accuracy, also analyzing whether it is amplified or concealed by the effect of vertical bias caused by vegetation (i.e., land cover). The terrain slope was derived from a lidar DTM at a 2 m resolution and aggregated to the resolution of each individual global DEM using a mean value (Moudrý et al., 2019).

2.6. Accuracy Assessment

2.6.1. Assessment of Global DEMs Accuracy

In this assessment, lidar DTM was used as the reference data and the vertical differences between lidar DTM and remaining models were calculated. We visualized the distributions of the height differences using density plots and summarized them by calculating three error metrics typically used in the literature (Höhle & Höhle, 2009): mean error (ME), mean absolute error (MAE), and root mean square error (RMSE) defined as follows:

$$\text{ME} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (h_{DEMi} - h_{REFi}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta h_i$$

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |h_{DEMi} - h_{REFi}| = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\Delta h_i|$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta h_i^2}$$

where h_{DEMi} is the i th elevation from the evaluated model, h_{REFi} is the corresponding elevation from the reference lidar DTM, and n is the number of elevation points (cells) sampled.

2.6.2. Assessment of Stream Network Delineation Accuracy

To derive a stream network from global DEMs and lidar DTM, we used the ArcGISPro tool “Derive Stream As Line.” In the first step, this tool fills in the depressions in the DEM (Metz et al., 2011). It utilizes the flow direction raster and the flow accumulation raster to delineate streams. The flow direction raster indicates the direction of water flow from each cell (using single flow direction (D8) algorithm; Jensen & Domingue, 1988) and was used as an input for the flow accumulation raster computation. The value of cells in this raster represents the number of upstream cells (i.e., the total area) that flow into each cell. High values of the flow accumulation raster indicate areas where flow is likely to converge, forming streams. By setting an accumulation threshold, the tool identifies cells that meet or exceed this value as streams. We tested multiple threshold values to balance the detection ability in a way identifying of relatively small streams while avoiding excessively small ones. This testing revealed a number of cells corresponding to 70 ha to be the optimal threshold. Note that this approach does not support modeling of bifurcations, which, in some cases, may have slightly affected our results.

Prior to calculating the following metrics, we removed water bodies from the stream network data sets. The resulting stream network was compared with the reference stream network (Section 2.3.2). For a quantitative analysis of the spatial relationships between the stream networks derived from global DEMs and the reference stream network, we computed the (a) number of intersecting points (i.e., points where the evaluated stream crosses the reference stream), (b) proportions (%) of vertices of the DEM-derived stream networks falling into each of eight buffer zones (0–5, 5–15, 15–20, 20–30, 30–40, 40–50, 50–60, 60–200 m) around the reference stream network. A greater proportion of vertices within narrower buffer zones indicates enhanced precision in spatial location (Peñas et al., 2011). Finally, we calculated (c) the average distance between DEM-derived and reference stream networks. We generated points at regular intervals of 500 m along each evaluated stream network and for each of these points, we then calculated the nearest distance to a reference stream. We calculated the mean distances for each evaluated data set according to land cover (urban, non-forest, and forest) and three slope categories (i.e., slope <10°, 10°–30°, and >30°). To ensure a fair comparison between the evaluated data sets, land cover and slope information is derived from the nearest point on the reference stream (not the modeled stream). This way, we evaluate conditions at the “true” location of the stream, which, however, may not match the location of the modeled stream due to poor terrain representation). A lower mean distance indicates superior accuracy.

Table 2

Evaluation of MERIT90, CON30, FAB30, SRTM90, TDX90, TDX12, NASA30, and COP30 Error for Urban, Non-Forest, and Forest Areas Relative to Lidar DTM

DEM	Urban areas			Non-forest areas			Forest areas						
	Num. of cells	ME [m]	MAE [m]	RMSE [m]	Num. of cells	ME [m]	MAE [m]	RMSE [m]	Num. of cells	ME [m]	MAE [m]	RMSE [m]	
Bare-earth	CON30	39k	0.4	2.2	3.5	343k	-1.1	2.3	3.3	849k	-1.8	5.3	6.7
	FAB30	39k	1.4	1.9	3.3	343k	0.6	1.5	3.1	850k	-0.7	5.8	7.3
	MERIT90	4k	3.1	3.5	4.6	36k	1.2	2.4	3.3	93k	2.1	4.9	6.3
Original	SRTM90	4k	3.4	3.6	5.2	36k	2.0	2.8	4.2	93k	8.5	8.9	10.9
	TDX90	4k	3.7	3.8	5.1	36k	2.3	2.7	4.5	93k	10.1	10.4	12.8
	TDX12	248k	3.4	3.5	5.9	2.1M	2.2	2.6	5.5	5.3M	10.2	10.5	13.6
	NASA30	39k	3.3	3.7	5.5	343k	2.2	3.1	4.8	850k	8.5	9.0	11.1
	COP30	39k	3.5	3.7	5.7	343k	2.3	2.8	5.2	850k	10.7	10.7	13.9

Note. The best (green) and worst (red) DEM for each metric is highlighted. k: thousands, M: millions.

3. Results

3.1. Accuracy Assessment of Global DEMs

The lowest error of the evaluated original DEMs (i.e., SRTM90, TDX90, NASA30, COP30, TDX12) was observed in non-forest areas, slightly higher in urban areas, and the highest error was observed in forest areas (Table 2; Figure 3). The RMSE was below 5.5 and 5.9 m in non-forest and urban areas, respectively. The density plots of height differences of all DEMs (Figure 3) show a unimodal distribution, with a peak near zero for non-forest areas and a peak slightly shifted to the positive values for urban areas. In forest areas, all original DEMs considerably overestimated the terrain (ME > 8 m) and the RMSEs reached up to 13.9 m (Figure 3, Table 2). The density plots of height differences of original DEMs show a bimodal distribution. This is especially evident for a highest resolution TDX12, with a considerably higher number of cells with a low (close to zero) error compared to for example, TDX90. These cells likely belong to non-forest areas (i.e., the improved resolution results in improved accuracy due to lower bias caused by vegetation) that were, due to the lower resolution of the land cover data (100 m), erroneously classified as forests. The distribution of height differences of the 90 m resolution DEMs closely matched that of their 30 m resolution counterparts across all land cover categories (Figure 3). However, the error was slightly lower for DEMs at a 90 m resolution. The RMSE and MAE of SRTM90 were lower than those of NASA30, and the RMSE and MAE of TDX90 were lower than those of COP30, respectively. Congruently, the RMSE of TDX12 was higher (by up to 1 m) than the RMSE of TDX90 in all land cover types. MAE showed only small differences between TDX12 and TDX90, indicating more outliers in TDX12 (Table 2).

In the category of bare-earth DEMs, FAB30 was the most accurate DEM in urban and non-forest areas (Table 2). In forest areas, MERIT90 was the most accurate DEM, with its RMSE of 6.3 m, followed by CON30 and FAB30 with RMSEs of 6.7 and 7.3 m, respectively. However, all bare-earth DEMs showed a notably greater density of values below zero compared to the original source DEMs, particularly in forested areas (Figure 3).

3.1.1. Effect of Slope on Global DEMs

Our results show a considerable effect of the terrain slope on the vertical accuracy of evaluated DEMs. The increasing slope was generally associated with increasing error and wider error distribution, particularly in non-forest areas (Figure 4). In these areas, the error metrics (i.e., ME, RMSE) of all DEMs exhibited an exponential increase across slope categories. A similar pattern was observed in urban areas, except for the 90-m resolution DEMs, the accuracy of which suddenly increased for slopes steeper than 25°. In forest areas, on the other hand, we can see an (inverse) quadratic dependence of DEMs error on the slope, except for CON30 (Figure 4). The lowest error metrics in all land cover and slope categories are generally yielded by the three bare-earth DEMs (i.e., FAB30, CON30, and MERIT90). All DEMs overestimated the terrain throughout all slope categories except for two bare-earth DEMs, namely CON30 and FAB30 (CON30 mainly underestimated the terrain, and FAB30 showed a mix of positive and negative mean errors in forests; Figure 4).

Figure 3. Distributions of height differences (compared to the lidar-derived DTM) for all evaluated DEMs for urban, non-forest, and forest areas. The vertical dashed line represents zero (i.e., perfect fit).

3.2. Stream Network Delineation

3.2.1. Quantitative Assessment

Stream networks derived from lidar DTM had the best accuracy in terms of the number of intersect points (Table 3) and the percentage of the vertices of reference streams within distance intervals (Figure 5). The coarser resolution of global DEMs limited the achievable detail and, therefore (compared to the streams derived from lidar DTM), the number of intersect points decreased considerably with coarser DEM resolution. Global DEMs with coarser resolution yielded a lower number of intersection points with reference streams, indicating more accurate stream network delineation using higher resolution DEMs (Table 3). In addition, the higher was a

Figure 4. Effect of the slope on the accuracy (ME, RMSE) of global DEMs in urban, forest, and non-forest areas. Note the increase in error with an increasing slope in non-forest areas in all models. In forests, this relationship is not that obvious, especially for very high slopes. Note the improved accuracy of bare-earth DEMs (dashed lines) compared to the original global DEMs (solid lines).

particular DEM's spatial resolution, the greater was the proportion of vertices falling within the narrower buffer distance categories (Figure 5).

Finally, the average distance of DEM-derived stream networks from reference streams was lower for bare-earth DEMs than for the original DEMs of the same resolution (Figure 6). However, it varied considerably across land cover and slope categories (Figure 6). In fact, land cover and slope affected the accuracy of the delineated stream networks more than the quality (i.e., resolution and vertical bias) of the adopted DEM (Figure 6). Streams were most accurate in forests, followed by non-forest areas and urban areas. With increasing slope, the accuracy tended to increase in all land cover categories. The most significant improvement with increasing slope was evident in non-forest and urban areas (Figure 6). This is in contrast to the land cover and slope effect on DEM accuracy, which had exactly the opposite effect (see previous sections).

Table 3
The Number of Points That Intersect Reference Streams in Individual Models

DEM	Number of intersect points
lidar DTM	38,067
CON30	5,167
FAB30	5,447
MERIT90	3,869
SRTM90	3,554
TDX90	3,408
TDX12	8,161
NASA30	5,151
COP30	5,484

3.2.2. Qualitative Assessment

The stream networks derived from global DEMs represent similar flow patterns (Figure 7). Considerable differences among derived stream networks exist at local scales. There are notable errors in the position of streams derived from global DEMs relative to reference data. For example, the position of the channel may be off by tens or even hundreds of meters (Figure 8a). As expected, the biggest differences are evident in the relatively flat areas on the Polish side of the mountains (Figure 7). The network extraction from DEMs with more detailed resolution (such as NASA30, FAB30, and, especially, TDX12) performed sub-optimally in areas with abrupt changes in vertical accuracy of determining terrain (e.g., forest boundaries or roads). In such places, the stream course is often erroneously copying such apparent “valleys” (Figure 8b). The relatively coarse resolution of global DEMs also generated channels with unnaturally straight sections and angular features, which led to inaccuracies, especially in meandering streams (Figure 8c).

Figure 5. Percentages of vertices of DEM-derived streams falling within seven buffer zones (i.e., categories of distance) from the reference stream network. Note the lower proportion of vertices in the close proximity to the reference stream in models with coarser resolution (MERIT90, TDX90, SRTM90). Note the improved accuracy of bare-earth DEMs (dashed lines) compared to the original global DEMs (solid lines) of the same resolution.

Figure 6. Average distance (in meters) of the evaluated DEM-derived streams from the reference stream network in three slope and land cover categories, respectively. Urban (U), non-forest (NF), and forest areas (F).

Relatively minor inaccuracies in stream network delineation were caused by the linear vegetation along streams, which caused vertical bias in global DEMs and resulted in shifts of derived streams of tens of meters (Figure 8d).

4. Discussion

Global space-borne DEMs are unsuitable surrogates for bare-earth in urban and particularly in forest areas as they all show considerable elevation bias relative to the terrain (e.g., Gdulová et al., 2020; Hawker et al., 2022; Li

Figure 7. River networks generated using the eight DEMs. Boxes indicate the positions of sites shown in detail in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Errors in stream network delineation typically appeared in areas (a) that were relatively flat, (b) of notable changes in DEMs vertical accuracy (e.g., roads or forest edges), (c) of meandering streams, (d) with linear vegetation along the streams.

et al., 2023; Shortridge & Messina, 2011). Therefore, significant efforts were made to remove this bias, which resulted in the availability of several so-called bare-earth DEMs (Hawker et al., 2022; Yamazaki et al., 2017). In this study, we compared the accuracy of three bare-earth DEMs (MERIT, FAB30, CON30) with several DEMs that were not processed to remove vegetation and/or buildings (NASA30, COP30, SRTM90, TDX90, TDX12). In particular, we concentrated on the success of vegetation and building offset removal in bare-earth DEMs, the role of land cover and terrain topography on the accuracy of DEMs, and the suitability of the DEMs for stream network delineation.

4.1. The Role of Land Cover and Vegetation Offset Removal

All evaluated global DEMs showed similar dependence of errors on the land cover type, irrespective of their resolution and mission (i.e., SRTM or TanDEM-X). The highest accuracy was observed in non-forest areas, followed by urban areas, and the lowest accuracies were recorded in forest areas (Figure 3), which corresponds to many previous studies (Gdulová et al., 2020; Hawker et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023; Shortridge & Messina, 2011). The vertical accuracy was much better for bare-earth DEMs (MERIT90, CON30, FAB30) than for DEMs that were not processed to remove vegetation and/or buildings. The vegetation removal procedure used for their construction was evidently successful (Figure 3); however, the success differed between the DEMs and land cover

types. FAB30 was the most accurate model in non-forest areas, while CON30 and MERIT90 suffered from under- and overestimation of bare earth, respectively. This corresponds to the results of the recent evaluation of global DEMs in India (Dandabathula et al., 2023) and the Ayeyarwady Delta in Myanmar (Seeger et al., 2023). The improvement in terms of RMSE between COP30 and FAB30 in urban areas was from 5.7 to 3.3 m, which aligns well with the results by Dandabathula et al. (2023), who reported a decrease in RMSE from approximately 6 to 3 m. In forests, however, FAB30 and CON30 tended to underestimate the terrain, with MERIT90 being the most accurate DEM (Table 2, Figure 4). In contrast, Hawker et al. (2022) and, more recently, Marsh et al. (2023) reported higher accuracy of FAB30 than of MERIT90. Despite its slightly lower accuracy in forests in our study area, FAB30 is clearly the most comprehensive bare-earth DEM. According to the RMSE, FAB30 was more accurate than TDX12 throughout all categories of land cover (Table 2). FAB30 is suitable for analyses in small forested catchments, as suggested by Marsh et al. (2023), as well as for analyses over large areas with varying land cover types as shown by our results. Note, however, that in forests, bare-earth DEMs had a higher density of negative vertical differences than COP30 and TDX90 (Figure 4), which likely resulted from the overestimation of the forest height during the vegetation bias removal. Further improvement of the procedures, including the adopted data, for vegetation offset removal is, therefore, required.

4.2. Effect of Terrain Slope

The terrain slope affects the vertical accuracy of all evaluated DEMs; however, the magnitude of the effect differs between the DEMs and land cover types. In non-forest areas (where all models should more or less represent the bare ground) vertical accuracy of global DEMs decreased considerably with increasing slope. The RMSEs of all models in non-forest areas at least doubled for slopes between 20° and 30° compared to slopes between 0° and 10°. A similar effect of the increasing slope on DEM accuracy was shown, for example, by Shortridge and Messina (2011) or Gdulová et al. (2020). However, the effect of the terrain slope on DEM accuracy is less evident in forest areas due to the prevailing effect of the vegetation-caused vertical bias (Figure 4). In other words, the vegetation bias considerably conceals the adverse impacts of steep terrain slopes. This contrasts with studies by Uuemaa et al. (2020) and Li et al. (2023), who concluded that slope is the most important factor affecting the DEM quality in mountain environments, followed by vegetation cover.

4.3. Stream Network Delineation

Several earlier studies have investigated the influence of DEM resolution and data sources on derived stream networks accuracy and showed improved stream network delineation with increasing resolution (Li & Wong, 2010; Murphy et al., 2008; Wang & Yin, 1998; Woodrow et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2014). Importantly, bare-earth DEMs with removed vegetation offsets were not employed in those analyses as they became available only relatively recently (Hawker et al., 2022; Yamazaki et al., 2017). It was, therefore, unclear whether higher resolution or vegetation offset removal is more important for accurate stream network delineation (but see Moges et al., 2023). Our study is the first one that assessed whether global DEMs with fine 12 m resolution (e.g., TanDEM-X) or bare-earth DEMs at 30 m resolution should be preferred for stream network delineation. The bare-earth DEMs, namely FAB30 and CON30, were among the best global DEMs for stream network delineation. They performed better than finer resolution TanDEM-X at 12 m in most slope and land cover categories (Figure 6). On the other hand, higher resolution of TDX12 provides better detail and allows the delineation of meandering streams with better accuracy than coarser resolution data (Figure 8c). Still, the very same reasons might result in the erroneous delineation of streams in areas with notable changes in vertical accuracy, such as roads within a forest (Figure 8b). Such errors are, however, relatively easy to detect using visual inspection and transportation network data; this issue should, therefore, not be viewed as a reason to use coarse resolution models.

4.4. Stream Network Delineation as a Metric for Assessing the Quality of DEMs

The need for accurate, open-access global DEMs continues to grow (Schumann & Bates, 2018), along with the need for comprehensive validation approaches (Bielski et al., 2023; Guth et al., 2024). Most studies validate global DEMs against more accurate reference data, such as ground control points measured by Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) and spaceborne or airborne lidar measurements (López-Vázquez & Ariza-López, 2023), typically considering only elevation differences and popular statistics such as mean error and root mean square error (e.g., Hawker et al., 2019; Meadows et al., 2024; Okolie et al., 2024). However, this approach

may fail to predict the effect of errors in DEMs on their final applications, and the need to move beyond the simple evaluation of elevation differences has been recently highlighted (Bielski et al., 2023; Trevisani et al., 2023). Alternatively, the quality of DEMs can be assessed in terms of the quality of the produced output, that is, in the context of a particular type of analysis (e.g., Huss & Pumar, 1997; Hutchinson & Dowling, 1991; Lagner et al., 2018).

The analysis of elevation differences alone cannot fully capture the capability of a DEM to reproduce stream flow. On the one hand, our results show that bare-earth DEMs have the highest vertical accuracy (Table 2) and that the stream networks derived from them yield a lower average distance from reference streams compared to those derived from the original DEMs of the same resolution (Figure 6). On the other hand, as the spatial resolution of a DEM increases, so does the quality of derived streams (Table 3, Figure 5). This, however, cannot be said of vertical accuracy, which often decreases with higher resolutions. For example, according to vertical accuracy characterized by RMSE (Table 2), the TanDEM-X DEM at a 12 m resolution is either the worst or second worst model, depending on the land cover category, and is always worse than the TanDEM-X DEM at 90 m resolution. Despite this, stream networks derived from the TanDEM-X DEM at a 12 m resolution exhibit the highest number of points intersecting reference streams (Table 3) and the greatest proportion of vertices within narrower buffer distance categories (Figure 5). This is likely due to the fact that DEM elevation values might have relatively low absolute vertical accuracy, but stream network delineation is particularly sensitive to DEM's relative vertical accuracy near the channel. If this relative accuracy is sufficient, it can yield correct results for the task (Wise, 2000).

Interestingly enough, our results show that the accuracy of derived stream networks is affected by terrain slope and land cover rather than by the absolute vertical accuracy of DEMs (Figure 6). In contrast to DEM accuracy, stream network delineation performed poorly in urban areas, slightly better in non-forest areas, and relatively well in forests. Similarly, while the accuracy of the DEM deteriorates with increasing slope, the accuracy of the delineated streams improves. This is not unexpected given that in flatter areas, even a relatively small error forming an apparent linear depression can easily be identified as a stream bed (Metz et al., 2011; Veregin, 1997). This underscores the need to include stream network delineation in the quality assessment of global DEMs. However, see Bielski et al. (2023), who showed that the combined criteria of elevation, slope, and roughness are also applicable in ranking DEMs with respect to their applicability in stream network delineation.

5. Conclusions

In this study, we evaluated (a) the accuracy of eight global DEMs with various resolutions and levels of editing (Table 1) and their usability for stream network delineation in a mountainous region of Central Europe. We assessed (b) the effect of land cover and terrain slope on the DEM accuracy and delineated stream networks accuracy and investigated (c) whether the higher resolution or vegetation offset removal is more important for accurate stream network delineation.

Our analysis showed the effect of land cover on the accuracy of all tested DEMs. The accuracy of all DEMs was the lowest in forest areas. The effect of slope on DEMs accuracy was particularly noticeable in non-forest areas, while it was less evident in forest areas where the vegetation bias considerably concealed the adverse impacts of steep terrain slopes. The vegetation removal procedure was successful for all bare-earth DEMs (MERIT, CEDTM, FABDEM), and their vertical accuracies in forests considerably improved. However, this procedure also resulted in a high density of negative vertical differences compared to the original DEMs. Therefore, further improvement of the procedures, including adopted data, for vegetation offset removal is required.

FABDEM can be recommended as the most appropriate model for hydrological (and other) studies involving large areas with different slopes and land cover categories. This is especially important with respect to the fact that the new version of the global HydroSHEDS database is going to be produced using hydrologically pre-conditioned TanDEM-X DEM at a 30 m resolution with removed vegetation and buildings offset. Assuming that the removal of vegetation will be as successful as in the case of FABDEM, we can expect a significant refinement of this database compared to its first version. However, TanDEM-X DEM exists also at a 12 m resolution, and our results show that resolution is equally important as the vegetation bias removal, enhancing the capability to identify meandering streams. On the other hand, it also brings challenges as it enhances the capability to identify features such as forest edges, roads, and railways, which can subsequently introduce inaccuracies into the delineated stream networks. This highlights that with the increasing resolution of global DEMs, vegetation

offset removal becomes more important for accurate stream network delineation. Therefore, a global bare-earth model based on the 12 m TanDEM-X would be a major achievement. Given the increasing availability of local and global high-resolution vegetation height models (Lang et al., 2023; Moudrý et al., 2024; Schwartz et al., 2023), this might not be such a distant future.

Data Availability Statement

All evaluated data are available free of charge: SRTM DEM (SRTM, 2013), NASADEM (NASA JPL, 2021), TanDEM-X DEM (DLR, 2018), Copernicus DEM (ESA, 2023), MERIT DEM (MERIT, 2017), FABDEM (Hawker & Neal, 2023), Continental Europe DEM (Hengl et al., 2020). Reference ALS point clouds for Czechia is available for download from the Czech National Geoportal (DMR5G, 2023). Reference ALS point clouds for Poland is available for download from the Polish National Geoportal (ISOK LiDAR, 2023). Data can be downloaded from section “Data for download—LiDAR measurements.” Reference stream network data were acquired from the Digital Database of Water Management Data (DIBAVOD, 2023), developed by the T.G. Masaryk Water Research Institute and from the Polish National Geoportal (ISOK Water, 2023), managed by the Head Office of Geodesy and Cartography.

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